

Impact Factor: 5.186

ISSN: 2181-0664

DOI: 10.26739/2181-0664

www.tadqiqot.uz

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

Special Issue 1

2023

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

1 МАХСУС СОН

ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ
СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫЙ НОМЕР 1

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL
SPECIAL ISSUE 1

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ | UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

№SI-1 (2023) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-0664-2023-SI-1>

Бош мухаррир:
Главный редактор:
Chief Editor:

Мадазимов Мадамин Муминович
Ректор Андижанского Государственного
медицинского института, д.м.н., профессор
кафедры факультетской и госпитальной
хирургии

Тахририят раиси:
Председатель редакционной коллегии:
Chairman of the editorial Board:

Алексеев Андрей Анатольевич
Директор ожогового центра НМИЦ хирургии
им. В.Вишневского, главный комбустиолог
Министерства здравоохранения России, д.м.н.,
профессор.

Бош мухаррир ўринбосари:
Заместитель главного редактора:
Deputy Chief Editor:

Салахиддинов Камалиддин Зухриддинович
доцент, д.м.н. кафедры факультетской и
госпитальной хирургии Андижанского
Государственного медицинского института

Бош мухаррир ўринбосари:
Заместитель главного редактора:
Deputy Chief Editor:

Хегай Любовь Николаевна
доцент, к.м.н., начальник отдела по координации
деятельности грантов Межвузовской научно-
исследовательской лаборатории Ташкентской
медицинской академии

Маъсул котиб:
Ответственный секретарь:
Executive Secretary:

Досина Маргарита Олеговна
в.н.с. ГНУ "Институт физиологии Национальной
академии наук Беларуси", к.б.н., председатель
Совета молодых ученых Отделения медицинских
наук НАН Беларуси

Маъсул котиб:
Ответственный секретарь:
Executive Secretary:

Ниязова Зебинисо Анваровна
PhD кафедры офтальмологии, детской
офтальмологии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ ТАХРИРИЙ МАСЛАХАТ КЕНГАШИ | РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ СОВЕТ ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ EDITORIAL BOARD OF THE UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

Хужамбердиев Мамазоир Ахмедович

д.м.н., профессор кафедры госпитальной терапии Андижанского Государственного медицинского института

Привалова Ирина Леонидовна

д.б.н., профессор кафедры нормальной физиологии Курского государственного медицинского университета,
заведующая лабораторией физиологии висцеральных систем НИИ физиологии (Курск)

Гаврилова Елена Анатольевна

д.м.н., профессор, заведующая кафедрой лечебной физкультуры и спортивной медицины Северо-западного
государственного медицинского университета им. И.И. Мечникова (Санкт-Петербург)

Чурганов Олег Анатольевич

д.п.н., профессор кафедры ЛФК и спортивной медицины Северо-Западного государственного
медицинского университета им. И.И. Мечникова (Санкт-Петербург)

Салахиддинов Зухриддин Салахиддинович

д.м.н., профессор, заведующий кафедрой ВОП №1, Андижанского государственного медицинского института

Рябчиков Денис Анатольевич

д.м.н., в.н.с. онкологического отделения хирургических методов лечения ФГБУ "НМИЦ
онкологии им. Н.Н. Блохина" Минздрава России

Гулямов Суръат Саидвалиевич

д.м.н., профессор кафедры оториноларингологии, детской оториноларингологии, стоматологии
Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Тереза Магалхайз
профессор, заведующая кафедрой Судебной медицины государственного университета Порту (Португалия)

Юлдашев Илхом Рузиевич
д.м.н., профессор, заведующий кафедрой Аллергологии, иммунологии, микробиологии
Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Хамраев Абдурашид Журакулович
д.м.н., профессор кафедры госпитальной детской хирургии, Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

РЕДАКЦИОННАЯ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Эрматов Низом Жумакулович
д.м.н., доцент, заведующий кафедрой гигиены детей и подростков и гигиены питания Ташкентской медицинской академии

Рузиев Шерзод Ибодуллаевич
д.м.н., доцент кафедры судебной медицины и медицинского права Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Якубова Олтиной Абдуганиевна
доктор медицинских наук, доцент, заведующая кафедрой акушерства и гинекологии, неонатологии факультета повышения квалификации и переподготовки врачей Андijanского государственного медицинского института

Бабич Светлана Михайловна
доцент, заведующая кафедрой социальной гигиены Андijanского государственного медицинского института

Сабирова Рихси Абдукадировна
д.м.н., профессор кафедры медицинской и биологической химии Ташкентской медицинской академии

Цеомашко Наталья Евгеньевна
д.б.н., с.н.с., заведующая отделом медико-генетических исследований МНИЛ Ташкентской медицинской академии

Хамраева Лола Салимовна
доцент, к.м.н. кафедры офтальмологии, детской офтальмологии Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Усманходжаева Адиба Амирсaidовна
доцент, к.м.н., заведующая кафедрой Народной медицины, реабилитологии и физической культуры Ташкентской медицинской академии

Тухтаева Нигора Хасановна
DSc, доцент кафедры пропедевтики внутренних болезней № 2, Ташкентской медицинской академии.

Шарипова Фарида Камилевна
к.м.н., доцент кафедры психиатрии, наркологии и детской психиатрии, медицинской психологии, психотерапии
Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Бузруков Батир Тулкунович
д.м.н., профессор, заведующий кафедрой офтальмологии, детской офтальмологии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

Туйчиев Галибжан Урмонжонович
к.м.н., доцент, заведующий кафедрой детской хирургии, детской анестезиологии-реаниматологии с курсом
офтальмологии и стоматологии факультета усовершенствования и переподготовки врачей АГМИ

Маматхужаева Гулнора Нажмитдиновна
доцент, к.м.н. кафедры Офтальмологии Андijanского Государственного медицинского института

Каримова Зиёда Кушбаевна
доцент, к.м.н. кафедры Аллергологии, клинической иммунологии, микробиологии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

Саидходжаева Саида Набиевна
доцент, Phd кафедры неврологии, детской неврологии и медицинской генетики Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

Зуфарова Зухра Хабибуллаевна
доцент, к.ф.н. кафедры промышленной технологии лекарственных средств Ташкентского фармацевтического института

Ибрагимова Марина Фёдоровна
PhD, ассистент кафедры N1 педиатрии и неонатологии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета.

Алимова Дурдона Дильмуратовна
PhD кафедры оториноларингологии, детской оториноларингологии, детской стоматологии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

Page Maker | Верстка | Сахифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

1. Primov F.Sh., Akilov B.B., Kurbonov J.R., Djuraev J.A. EVOLUTION OF VIEWS AND MODERN TRENDS IN ENDOVISUAL SURGICAL TREATMENT FOR URGENT ABDOMINAL PATHOLOGY IN CHILDREN.....	7
2. Pulatova Sh.Kh. A NEW APPROACH TO THE TREATMENT OF TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS WITH CORONARY HEART DISEASE.....	14
3. Pulatova Sh.Kh., Tasheva F.A. A NEW APPROACH TO THE TREATMENT OF DIABETIC NEPHROPATHY WITH HEART FAILURE.....	20
4. Khamroev E.E., Pulatova Sh.Kh. THE CHOICE OF MEDICINAL PRODUCTS FOR CHRONIC HEART FAILURE OF VARIOUS GENESIS IN THE ELDERLY.....	26
5. Rasulova Nodira Alisherovna, Khojaeva Nikzan Nazarbekovna INFLUENCE OF 25(OH)D ON THE CAUSES OF RICKETS IN CHILDREN.....	34
6. Natalya Vladimirovna Voronina, Matluba Shamtsudinova SANITARY AND HYGIENIC MONITORING OF PESTICIDE POLLUTION OF FOOD PRODUCTS IN UZBEKISTAN.....	39
7. Rasulova Nadira Alisherovna, Khakimova Sohiba Ziyadullayevna THE USE OF MUSIC THERAPY FOR THE CORRECTION OF PSYCHOSOMATIC DISORDERS IN CHILDREN.....	46
8. Abdieva Yulduz Atakulovna, Agzamova Gulnara Sunnatovna CHANGES IN THE CYTOKINE PROFILE IN PATIENTS WITH SILICOSIS IN COMBINATION WITH CORONARY HEART DISEASE AND ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION.....	50
9. Davlatova Dilrabo, Usmanova Shoirra THE ROLE OF ENDOTHELIAL DYSFUNCTION IN THE PATHOGENESIS OF INFLAMMATORY PERIODONTAL DISEASES.....	57
10. Nozima Tokhirzhonovna Mavlyanova, Nazifa Valievna Agzamova CLINICAL AND ECONOMIC ANALYSIS AND ITS POSSIBILITIES IN THE EVALUATION OF THE USE OF ANTIBACTERIAL DRUGS.....	64
11. Kamilov Khaydar, Usmanova Lazzat, Akhmadaliev N.N. DYNAMICS OF THE CYTOKINE PROFILE OF THE ORAL FLUID IN PATIENTS WITH SETTON'S APHTHOSIS.....	67
12. Mirzaev Husanjon, Rizaev Eler FEATURES OF THE CLINICAL COURSE AND FREQUENCY OF OCCURRENCE OF PERIODONTAL DISEASES AND ORAL MUCOSA IN PATIENTS SUFFERING FROM CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE.....	73

13. Mirzaev Husanjon, Rizaev Eler THE NATURE OF CHANGES IN BIOMARKERS OF KIDNEY DAMAGE IN SALIVA, BLOOD AND URINE IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC GENERALIZED PERIODONTITIS....	79
14. Davlatova Dilrabo, Usmanova Shaira ENDOTHELIAL CELL DYSFUNCTION BY CHRONIC GENERALIZED PERIODONTITIS IN PATIENTS WITH ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION.....	85
15. Kamilov Kh.P., Kahharova D.J. HUMAN PAPILLOMA VIRUS AND ORAL MUCOSA LESIONS: INCREASED POTENTIAL OF MALIGNANT DEGENERATION.....	89
16. Rasulov A.B., Arifov S.S., Zufarov A.A. ON THE ISSUE OF HEARING SCREENING AMONG PREMATURE NEWBORNS.....	94
17. Yusupova Shahnoza EFFICIENCY OF IMIQUIMOD IN TREATMENT OF CONDYLOMA ACUMINATA.....	100

ISSN: 2181-0664

www.tadqiqot.uz

**Khamroev E.E.,
Pulatova Sh.Kh.**Republican Scientific Center of emergency
medical care of the Bukhara branch**THE CHOICE OF MEDICINAL PRODUCTS FOR CHRONIC HEART FAILURE OF
VARIOUS GENESIS IN THE ELDERLY** <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7782927>**ABSTRACT**

In economically developed countries, CHF accounts for 2.1% of the entire population, while more than 90% of women and about 75% of men with CHF are patients older than 70 years (V. A. Gv a 11 et al., 1998). In Russia, the elderly includes people aged 60 to 75 years, aged 75 to 90 years — people in old age and over 90 years — centenarians. In the USA and European countries, the elderly includes people aged 75-90 years ("young elderly"), over the age of 90 years — "old elderly", centenarians. The increase in the frequency of CHF with age is due to a number of significant factors: the undoubted growth in the modern world of coronary heart disease, HYPERTENSION— the main "suppliers" of CHF, especially with their frequent combination; certain successes in the treatment of acute and chronic forms of coronary heart disease, blood pressure, which contributed to the chronization of these diseases increase the life expectancy of such patients with the development of decompensation of blood circulation. In addition, the increase in the frequency of CHF with age is due to the formation of a "senile heart" with the accumulation of amyloid and lipofuscin in cardiomyocytes, sclerosis and myocardial atrophy, an increase in the processes of atherosclerosis not only of the main arteries, but also arteriosclerosis, hyalinosis of small and minute arteries, arterioles.

Keywords: CHF, old age, ACE inhibitors, diuretics, beta blockers and glycosides.

**Хамроев Э.Э.,
Пулатова Ш.Х.**Республиканский научный центр экстренный
медицинской помощи Бухарского филиала**ВЫБОР ЛЕКАРСТВЕННЫХ СРЕДСТВ ПРИ ХРОНИЧЕСКОЙ СЕРДЕЧНОЙ
НЕДОСТАТОЧНОСТИ РАЗЛИЧНОГО ГЕНЕЗА У ЛИЦ ПОЖИЛОГО ВОЗРАСТА****АННОТАЦИЯ**

В экономически развитых странах ХСН составляет 2,1 % от всей популяции, при этом более 90 % женщин и около 75 % мужчин с ХСН— это пациенты старше 70 лет (В. А. Гв а 11 е т а 1., 1998). В России к пожилым относятся лица в возрасте от 60 до 75 лет, в возрасте от 75 до 90 лет — лица в старческом возрасте и свыше 90 лет — долгожители. В США и европейских странах к пожилым относятся лица в возрасте 75—90 лет («молодые пожилые»), в возрасте

свыше 90 лет — «старые пожилые», долгожители. Увеличение частоты ХСН с возрастом обусловлено рядом существенных факторов: несомненным ростом в современном мире ИБС, АГ — основных «поставщиков» ХСН, особенно при их нередком сочетании; определенными успехами в лечении острых и хронических форм ИБС, АД, что способствовало хронизации этих заболеваний, увеличению продолжительности жизни подобных пациентов с развитием декомпенсации кровообращения. Кроме того, увеличение частоты ХСН с возрастом обусловлено формированием «старческого сердца» с накоплением амилоида и липофусцина в кардиомиоцитах, склерозом и атрофией миокарда, нарастанием процессов атеросклероза не только магистральных артерий, но и артериосклероза, гиалиноза мелких и мельчайших артерий, артериол.

Ключевые слова: ХСН, пожилой возраст, АПФ ингибиторы, диуретики, бета блокаторы и гликозиды.

Хамроев Е. Е.,
Пулатова Ш.Х.

Республика шошилинич тиббий ёрдам
илмий маркази Бухоро филиали

КЕКСА ОДАМЛАРДА ТУРЛИ ХИЛ ГЕНЕЗИСНИНГ СУРУНКАЛИ ЮРАК ЕТИШМОВЧИЛИГИ УЧУН ДОРИВОР МАҲСУЛОТЛАРНИ ТАНЛАШ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Иқтисодий ривожланган мамлакатларда сурункали юрак етишмовчилиги бутун аҳолининг 2,1% ни ташкил қилади, аёлларнинг 90% дан ортиғи ва ЧФ билан касалланган еракларнинг тахминан 75% 70 ёшдан катта беморлардир (В. а гв а 11 и другие., 1998). Россияда қарияларга 60 ёшдан 75 ёшгача, 75 ёшдан 90 ёшгача бўлган одамлар — кекса ёшдаги ва 90 ёшдан ошган одамлар — юз йилликлар киради. Ақш ва Европа мамлакатларида қарияларга 75-90 ёшдаги одамлар ("ёш қариялар"), 90 ёшдан ошганлар — "кекса қариялар", юз йилликлар киради. Yoshi билан ЧФ частотасининг ошиши бир қатор муҳим омилларга боғлиқ: коронер юрак касалликларининг замонавий дунёсида шубҳасиз ўсиш— гипертензия-ЧФнинг асосий "етказиб берувчилари", айниқса уларнинг тез-тез комбинацияси билан; ўткир ва чни даволашда маълум муваффақиятлар ва коронер юрак касаллигининг сурункали шакллари, қон босими, бу касалликларнинг хронизациясига ёрдам берган, қон айланишининг декомпенсацияси ривожланиши билан бундай беморларнинг умр кўриш давомийлигини оширади. Бундан ташқари, yoshi билан ЧФ частотасининг ошиши кардиёмиёситларда амилоид ва липофуссин тўпланиши билан "кекса юрак" шаклланиши, склероз ва миокард атрофияси, нафақат асосий артерияларнинг атеросклероз жараёнларининг кучайиши, балки артериосклероз, гиалиноз. кичик ва миёкард атрофияси. дақиқали артериялар, артериолалар билан боғлиқ.

Калит сўзлар: сурункали юрак етишмовчилиги (СЮЕ), қарилик, АПФ ингибиторлари, диуретиклар, бетта блокерлар ва гликозидлар.

Introduction. In order to more clearly understand the features of therapy in elderly and senile patients, it is necessary to consider issues related to changes in the functions of the cardiovascular system, the reaction of an aging organism to drug effects. Changes in the functions and structure of the heart and blood vessels with age are generally as follows:

1. A decrease in sympathetic reactivity contributes to a change in the heart's response to stress.
2. Vascular resistance increases as the elasticity of the vessels decreases, which increases the work of the myocardium and increases its oxygen consumption (SV at rest decreases with age — by the age of 70 it is 25% less than in 20 years; heart rate is reduced, UO decreases; peak heart rate decreases on load, MO)
3. The duration of LV reduction increases.

4. Changes in collagen tissue lead to an increase in the passive stiffness of the heart, i.e. a decrease in malleability (thickening of the LV walls). Focal fibrosis, changes in valve tissue are often observed; their calcification contributes to hemodynamic shifts. With aging, the number of nuclei in the valves decreases, there is an accumulation of lipids in the fibrous stroma, collagen degeneration, calcification. The aortic valve is more altered than the mitral valve, calcification of the valves is found in at least 1/3 of persons over 70 years of age. Sclerotic aortic stenosis and mitral insufficiency are more common.

The number of pacemaker cells is decreasing, fibrosis and microcalcification of the elements of the conducting system are increasing. Thickening and fibrosis increase the rigidity of blood vessels, which is expressed in the growth of OPSS. The reactivity of baroreceptors decreases, the number of p-adrenoreceptors decreases, their function worsens. Under the influence of the aging process, the functional reserve of the heart is significantly reduced. Among people over 65 years of age (Lavarenne et al., 1983), 30% of complications from drug therapy were noted. Medications acting on the cardiovascular system are the cause of 31.3% of complications. The bioavailability of many drugs increases due to the inhibition of their metabolism. The rate of elimination of drugs by the kidneys is reduced due to impaired function of the latter.

Adverse reactions when taking medications in the elderly occur noticeably more often and are more severe. Overdose of diuretics can lead to dangerous complications (as well as sedatives and glycosides). In the elderly, a smaller number of medications should be prescribed, if possible, at a minimum dose and with a simple regimen of their administration (sometimes written explanations are required!). It should also be borne in mind that prolonged bed rest and immobility often have an unfavorable therapeutic and psychological effect. When prescribing drug therapy in the elderly and senile age, the following should be taken into account: — there is no clinically significant change in the ability to absorb drugs

The main reasons for the peculiarities of drug exposure in the elderly:

Change	Pharmacological reason
Deceleration of suction	An increase in the pH of gastric juice Slowing evacuation from the stomach A decrease in intestinal motility and the rate of its emptying
Slowing down the distribution	Tendency to hypoalbuminemia Decrease in organ blood flow Decrease in intercellular fluid Increase in adipose tissue mass
Reducing the speed of transformation	Decreased activity of liver enzymes, hepatic blood flow
Slowing of excretion	Reduction of renal blood flow
Slowing down the metabolism	Increased bioavailability of drugs, high effect of primary passage

— the total volume of water in the body of the elderly is reduced, with the introduction of a water-soluble drug, its concentration increases, with the use of a fat-soluble drug, it decreases;

— increased bioavailability is due to a decrease in metabolism during the first passage;

— kidney function worsens with age, drug elimination decreases (especially drugs with a low therapeutic index, digoxin, etc.);

— the severity and duration of the drug's action depend not only on pharmacokinetic changes, but also on how it is modified;

— severe adverse reactions in the elderly are more likely to occur when using the following five groups of drugs: cardiac glycosides, diuretics, hypotensive agents, antiarrhythmics, anticoagulants;

— there may be dehydration, mental disorders, hyponatremia, hypokalemia, cerebral and thrombotic complications, orthostatic hypotension;

- it is necessary to prescribe as few medications as possible in the minimum dosage, for a short time, with a simple way of taking them and regimen;
- it is necessary to identify and, if possible, eliminate the causes of HF, improve the pumping function of the heart, correct the retention of water and salts;
- it is important to use diuretics, vasodilators and ACE inhibitors;
- it is necessary to avoid a fairly rapid overdose of diuretics, cardiac glycosides, sedatives;
- increased blood pressure requires adequate treatment;
- it is necessary to limit salt intake (<5 g / day)

The features of the action of drugs in the elderly, as well as the main causes of these features are presented in Table 1. Three "golden" rules for prescribing medicines to elderly patients were formulated by J.B. Schwartz (1998); 1) start treatment with small doses of the drug (1/2 of the usual dose); 2) slowly increase the dosage; 3) monitor for possible side effects

Myocardial damage in the elderly is noted in all forms of coronary heart disease, which occur against the background of already existing organic and functional changes in the heart and blood vessels of an age-related nature. The causes of exacerbations of CHF in the elderly may be transient painful and pain-free myocardial ischemia, atypical myocardial infarction, cardiac arrhythmias (paroxysmal and tachyarrhythmic forms of atrial fibrillation, ventricular arrhythmias of high gradations in Weight, sinus node weakness syndrome, etc.). Numerous negative extracardial effects are also important - pulmonary embolism, acute infections, renal failure, respiratory failure, uncorrectable hypertension, etc

It is also necessary to take into account patients' non-compliance with the regimen and treatment regimen, alcohol abuse, physical and emotional overload, uncontrolled medication (antiarrhythmics, p-blockers, calcium antagonists, corticosteroids, nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, diuretics, vasodilators, hypotensive agents, etc.). The complexity of the diagnosis and treatment of CHF in the elderly is due to the presence of multiple organ failure, more frequent complications, including cardiac arrhythmias, polymorbidity, including combination with type 2 diabetes mellitus, dyscirculatory encephalopathy, bronchoobstructive diseases

With CHF, the elderly and elderly often do not have manifest symptoms of HF. Its manifestations may be a feeling of lack of air, shortness of breath during physical exertion and without it, coughing, tachycardia, cardiac arrhythmias. Disorders of cerebral circulation are not uncommon — increased ("causeless") fatigue, decreased physical and mental performance, dizziness, tinnitus, sleep disturbance, excitement, followed by prolonged depression. The main drugs used to treat CHF in the elderly:

Group of drugs	International name of drugs	Dose and frequency of administration per day	ACE
Captopril	Enalapril	Cilazapril	Perindopril
Quinapril	Ramipril	Fosinopril	Trandolapril
6,25-50 mg	3 times	10-20	1 time
0.5-5 mg	1 time	2-4	1 time
5-40	1-2 times	2.5-5	1 time
5-20	1-2 times	0.5-1.5	1 time

1. Diuretics Hypothiazide Chlorthalidone Furosemide Ethacric acid 25-100 mg/ day 25-100 mg/ day 20-100 mg/ day 5-100 mg/ day
2. Aldosterone antagonists Spironolactone, veroshpiron, al-dakton 25-100 mg/ day
3. Cardiac glycosides Digoxin 0.125-0.250 mg/ day
4. p-blockers Metoprolol Bisoprolol Carvedilol Nebivolol 6,25-100 mg / day 1,25-10 mg / day 6,25-50 mg / day 5-10 mg / day
5. Calcium channel blockers Verapamil SR Diltiazem Amlodipine 40-120 mg 2 times 30-90 mg 3 times 2.5-5 1 time
6. Peripheral vasodilators Nitroglycerin (tablets) Nitroglycerin (ointment) Nitroglycerin (patch) Isosorbide dinitrate Monocinque, Olikard retard Sodium Nitroprusside Hydralazine 6.5-19.5 mg 3 times 1- 5 cm 4 times 5-30 mg 1-2 times 10-60 mg 4-6 times 40-50 mg 1 time 0.5-10 mcg/ kg/min 25-75 mg 3-4 times

Peripheral edema in elderly people is not necessarily a consequence of CHF. They may be associated with increased hydrophilicity of tissues, a decrease in colloidal osmotic blood pressure, a slowdown in blood flow, a decrease in the filtration capacity of the kidneys, varicose veins, adynamia, chronic kidney and liver diseases, etc. Of particular note is the so-called chronic left ventricular

insufficiency with the phenomena of incipient pulmonary edema. These conditions of recurrent cardiac asthma can stop on their own, and sometimes require urgent care. The presented features of HF in the elderly cause undoubted diagnostic difficulties, require individual treatment and motor rehabilitation. The features of treatment include:

- early appointment of diuretics — from the initial stages of HF at first for a short time, then by courses and combined;
- early use of peripheral vasodilators, mainly nitrates, ace inhibitors, calcium antagonists;
- the appointment of cardiac glycosides for certain indications and in doses appropriate to senile age;
- if possible, sufficiently active motor rehabilitation.

Treatment of CHF in the elderly requires a number of additional conditions, taking into account considerable diagnostic difficulties and side effects of drug therapy.

It should be borne in mind that there are drugs that are not recommended for use in CHF in the elderly. These include: nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, corticosteroids, class I antiarrhythmic drugs (quinidine, disopyramide, ethacizine, etmosine, etc.). The pharmacokinetics of the elderly are:

- increased absorption of sublingual forms due to hyposalivation and xerostomia;
- slowing down the absorption of skin ointments, medicines from patches due to a decrease in the resorptive properties of the skin;
- prolongation of the half-life for enteral forms due to a decrease in the activity of liver enzymes;
- high severity of hemodynamic reactions during administration of the drug

Changes in the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of drugs in the elderly should take into account the individualization of the dose of the drug and its possible change. It is often necessary to treat the underlying and concomitant disease, taking into account frequent polymorbidity. Correction of doses of medicines is required (more often in the direction of reduction!) taking into account the age-related decline in the functions of various organs and systems. It is necessary to keep in mind the frequent development of adverse reactions during drug treatment. Finally, it is in elderly patients with CHF that a decrease in adherence to treatment should be taken into account, often due to a decrease in memory and/ or intelligence. When using diuretics, it is necessary to take into account a number of features of the senile organism: manifestations of cellular dehydration; redistribution of electrolytes between the cell and the environment with a tendency to hypokalemia; the peculiarity of age-related neuroendocrine regulation; age-related features of water and electrolyte metabolism.

All of the above, apparently, involves the use of diuretics in a lower dose, as short courses as possible, with mandatory monitoring and correction of the electrolyte profile and acid-base state of the body, compliance with the water-salt regime, respectively, the stage of CHF. With CHF I-II FC, the daily intake of liquid is no more than 1500 ml, table salt — 5.0—3.0 g; with CHF P-SHFC: liquid - 1000-1200 ml, table salt - 3,0-2,0-1,5 g; with CHF IV FC: liquid - 900/700 ml, table salt — 1.5-1.0 g. The sequence of diuretics in geriatric patients with CHF is determined individually in each case, but usually they start with the use of dichlorothiazide (hypothiazide), then triamterene with spironolactone (veroshpiron, aldactone) and, finally, loop diuretics (furosemide, lasix, uregit) are prescribed. In cases of severe CHF (Sh— IV FC), various combinations of diuretics are prescribed with the indispensable use of furosemide. Unfortunately, it is in the elderly with CHF that quite quickly

Excessive diuretic therapy in elderly patients can contribute to hypokalemia and a decrease in SV, a decrease in renal blood flow and filtration with the onset of azotemia. Thiazide diuretics are especially unfavorable in this regard. With the development of renal insufficiency against the background of the use of potassium-saving drugs, hyperkalemia occurs, manifested by rigidity and paresthesia in the extremities with muscle weakness, dyspeptic disorders (abdominal pain, metallic taste in the mouth, nausea, vomiting, etc.). At the same time, an ECG may record a slowdown in intraventricular conduction, an increase in the amplitude of the wave T. The means of correcting

hyperkalemia is repeated intravenous administration of sodium bicarbonate solutions, calcium gluconate

A reduction in the volume of intracellular fluid caused by taking diuretics can lead to hyperglycemia, increased blood viscosity, and microcirculation disorders. At the same time, the threat of thromboembolic complications increases. Diuretics (especially thiazide) contribute to the retention of uric acid, hyperuricemia, lead to severe arthralgia. Table 3 shows possible side effects and contraindications to the use of diuretics in geriatric practice. With prolonged use of diuretics, elderly patients with CHF often develop refractory to them. The causes of this phenomenon are hypokalemia, hyponatremia dilution, metabolic alkalosis, age-related hypo-albuminemia. This is facilitated by an increase in the activity of ADH and mineralocorticoid function of the adrenal glands in old age.

The use of diuretics in gerontological practice requires knowledge of possible side effects and frequent contraindications when prescribing them, as well as the interaction of diuretics with other medications. The doses of diuretics and their combinations should be determined on a case-by-case basis. However, the general trend of geriatric pharmacology towards lower doses of diuretics persists. The pharmacokinetics of cardiac glycosides in the elderly has its own characteristics: — increased absorption in the intestine due to a weakening of peristalsis and a tendency to constipation; — an increase in the content of the active free fraction in blood plasma due to age-related al-buminemia and a decrease in the amount of water in the body; — slowing down the excretion of glycosides by the kidneys and slowing down their biotransformation in the liver (this applies mainly to digoxin). These features, with the same dose of the drug, ensure the concentration of cardiac glycosides in the blood plasma in the elderly by 1.5-2 times.

The pharmacodynamics of cardiac glycosides in old age also has certain features: - increased sensitivity and decreased tolerance of the myocardium to cardiac glycosides; — more pronounced arrhythmogenic effect and greater drug resistance. Age-related features of pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics determine not only the severity of the cardiotoxic effect, but also the speed of onset of glycoside intoxication. At the same time, the threat of side effects during glycosidotherapy is high. Possible reactions of interaction of diuretics with other drugs

Diuretic Interaction with drugs Possible reactions of interaction.

Hypothyazid	Digoxin	Quinidine	Hypotensive preparations	Lithium salts	Increased risk of intoxication
Increased toxicity	Increased hypotensive effect	Increased toxicity	Furosemide	Amionoglycoside	antibiotics
Tseporin	Indomethacin	Aspirin	Cardiac glycosides	Increased ototoxicity	Nephrotoxicity
Decreased diuretic effect	The same	Increased risk of glycoside intoxication	Spironolactone	Indomethacin, aspirin	Antihypertensive drugs
Weakening of the diuretic effect	Strengthening of the antihypertensive effect	Uregit	Tseporin	Corticosteroids	Nephrotoxicity
Increased risk of gastrointestinal bleeding					

The optimal therapeutic effect in geriatric patients is accompanied by the following phenomena:

— positive dynamics of the general condition and well-being of the patient (reduction of shortness of breath, disappearance of attacks of suffocation, increased diuresis, reduction of congestion in the lungs, reduction of liver size, edema)

— reduction of heart rate to 60-80 in 1 minute; — positive reaction to individual physical activity. During therapy, elderly people often (up to 40%) show symptoms of glycoside intoxication: disorders of the heart, gastrointestinal tract and nervous system. It should be noted quite frequent neurological symptoms in the elderly and elderly: increased fatigue, insomnia, dizziness, confusion. "digitalis dilirium", syncopal state and the color of the surrounding in yellow or green

Peculiar risk factors for glycoside intoxication in old age are increased adrenergic effects on the heart, hypoxia, myocardial dystrophy, dilation of cavities, as well as frequent interaction of cardiac glycosides with other drugs. It should be pointed out that various metabolic agents (ATP, cocarboxylase, riboxin, neoton, preductal, etc.) are widely used in glycosidotherapy in geriatric practice, as well as correction of possible neuropsychiatric disorders.

The features of the pharmacotherapy of coronary heart disease in the elderly include the following:

- for the relief and prevention of angina attacks, the spray is the priority form;
- course therapy: retarded forms of one or two doses (isosorbide dinitrate, I-5-M);
- with a decrease in memory, physical activity, it is advisable to use skin patches with nitroglycerin; — restriction in the use of buccal forms due to frequent pathology of the oral cavity;
- it is necessary to take into account the patient's commitment to a certain [5]

Tolerance to nitrates is a real problem in the elderly with coronary heart disease. The retarded form of isosorbide dinitrate is most effective in the elderly - the dose is quite high — from 120 to 180 mg / day, the most dynamic is painful, not painless myocardial ischemia. Nitroglycerin in geriatric patients often causes headache, nausea, decreased blood pressure with reflex tachycardia. Contraindications to the appointment of nitrates are severe arterial hypotension, glaucoma, cerebral hemorrhage, increased intracranial pressure. Prolonged preparations of nitroglycerin (sus-tak, nitrong, nitromac, nitrosorbide, isomac, isoket, isodinite, etc.) are less likely to cause headaches, but give other side effects; derivatives of isosorbide dinitrate have not only antianginal, but also hemodynamic properties, and therefore are successfully used in the treatment of CHF in the elderly [4]/

After a few weeks, some patients become addicted to nitrates. The effectiveness of the drugs is noticeably reduced and, what is practically important, does not increase with an increase in single and daily doses. Hemodynamic and antianginal effects of nitrates do not occur. In such cases, the doses of nitrates should be gradually reduced until complete withdrawal. After 1-2 weeks. sensitivity to nitrates may recover. It is possible to use mononitrates— olikard, monochinque, etc., which give less tolerance and a greater hemodynamic effect. Direct vasodilators (nitroglycerin and its derivatives, isosorbide dinitrate, mononitrates, etc.) are widely used in the treatment of OSN (pulmonary edema, cardiogenic shock, etc.), as well as in pain forms and other pain-free variants of chronic coronary heart disease in the elderly, combined with CHF. The use of these drugs makes it possible to achieve an antianginal effect by reducing myocardial ischemia.

In recent years, materials have appeared on the cardio-protective effect of mononitrates (olikard, monochinque, etc.) in CHF. When they were prescribed with other cardiotropic drugs (ACE inhibitors, cardiac glycosides, etc.), a significant improvement in the main hemodynamic parameters in the treatment of CHF in the elderly was revealed. Negative phenomena when using parenteral nitrates in the elderly occur in 40% of cases and more often (the sharpest headache, nausea, etc.). Headache is associated with venous stasis, sharp arteriolodilation of cerebral vessels. With severe headache, it is possible to use caffeine-sodium benzoate inside in the form of a solution (1 ampoule of caffeine solution for 5-7 ml of 40% glucose solution). Molsidomine also quite often (about 20% of cases) causes headache, dizziness and nausea [3].

When using hydralazine hydrochloride (apressin) in the elderly, headache, nausea and vomiting, palpitations, hyperemia of the skin, a feeling of heat and burning in the eyes occur more often than in middle-aged people. The use of sodium nitroprusside and prazosin in the elderly, especially without detailed clinical and hemodynamic control, may be accompanied by side effects in the form of headache, nausea and vomiting, abdominal pain, hyperthermia, irritability, an increase in the number of angina attacks

ACE inhibitors are widely used in the treatment of CHF in elderly patients. They have displaced cardiac glycosides and peripheral vasodilators in geriatric practice. Possible side effects of ACE inhibitors include skin rash, dry cough, loss of taste sensations, glomerulopathy (proteinuria), excessive arterial hypotension. When prescribing ACE inhibitors to the elderly, it is necessary to exclude previous renal pathology (diffuse glomerulonephritis, pyelonephritis) in the stage of CRF, careful titration of the dose of the drug to prevent uncontrolled arterial hypotension. It is in the elderly with CHF that it is advisable to use ACE inhibitors with a distinct long-term, prolonged effect that do not cause hypotension of the first dose. These include perindopril - 2-4 mg / day, quinapril — 2.55 mg / day [2].

The appointment of ACE inhibitors is advisable for all classes of CHF, with left ventricular dysfunction, not yet accompanied by symptoms of CHF. This is relevant for patients with myocardial infarction with latent HF; they can be used with preserved LV systolic function, preventing the

development of overt HF and prolonging the period before decompensation occurs. The positive effect of ACE inhibitors on heart rhythm disorders, atherogenesis, kidney function, etc. was revealed. When prescribing ACE inhibitors to elderly with CHF, a number of principles should be taken into account: this is, first of all, verified HF, the absence of contraindications to the use of ACE inhibitors; special care should be taken with CHF I V FC according to NYNA, an increase in creatinine levels over 200 mmol / l, symptoms of generalized atherosclerosis. Treatment should begin with minimal doses: captopril — 6.25 mg 3 times a day, enalapril — 2.5 mg 2 times, quinapril — 2.5 mg 2 times, perindopril - 2 mg 1 time. Doses are doubled every 3-7 days. If necessary, the titration rate can be increased.

The appointment of ACE inhibitors requires taking into account a number of points: the effectiveness of the drug, the ease of selecting an adequate dose; the absence of the effect of the first dose in terms of collapse hypotension; side effects and tolerability; availability; adherence to the drug; price. It is possible to use p-blockers in the treatment of CHF in the elderly. It takes into account, first of all, the anti-tachycardial effect of the drug, its effect on the suppression of neurohumoral factors of HF. Side effects of p-blockers are primarily associated with their ability to cause sinus bradycardia, slowing of sinoauricular, atrioventricular and, to a lesser extent, intragastric conduction, a certain decrease in the pumping function of the heart, arterial hypotension, bronchospasm

The initial single dose of propranolol should not exceed 10 mg, then 20 mg, and a daily dose of 80 mg. The drugs of choice are cardioselective beta-blockers — metoprolol, bisoprolol, car-vedilol, nebivolol, etc. A single dose of metoprolol should not exceed 12.5-25 mg, daily — 75-100 mg. Contraindications to the appointment of beta-blockers are acute bradycardia and hypotension, sinus node weakness syndrome, atrioventricular blockades, bronchial asthma and asthmatic bronchitis in the acute stage, severe diabetes mellitus. The use of calcium antagonists in the elderly is especially indicated when CHF is combined with hypertension, including isolated systolic hypertension. The undoubted advantages are slow—acting, prolonged calcium antagonists - amlodipine, felodipine, altiazem, diltiazem [1]

Side effects when using calcium antagonists in the elderly are manifested by headache, edema of the lower extremities associated with the condition of peripheral vessels, slowing of sinoatrial and atrioventricular conduction, sinus tachycardia.

References.

1. Pulatova, Sh. X. (2012). Founders: Institute of Immunology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. OF THEORETICAL AND CLINICAL MEDICINE
2. Pulatova, Sh. X. (2012). Founders: Institute of Immunology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Founders: Institute of Immunology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan ISSN: 2091-5853
3. Khamroev, E. E., Nurboev, F. E., & Pulatova, S. K. (2022). CHRONIC HEART FAILURE: FEATURES CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS IN THE ELDERLY. British Medical Journal, 2(2).
4. Pulatova Sh.H. Method of improving vasopressor therapy for acute myocardial infarction complied with cardiogenetic shock // American Journal Of Medicine And Medical Sciences. 2020.– Vol. 10 (11). – P. 911-913
5. Pulatova Sh.H. Improvement of treatment of patients with acute heart failure, a comparative evaluation of the effectiveness of dobutamine and levosimendan// World Journal Of Pharmaceutical Research. 2020. Vol 9 (6). –P. 2283-2288

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

1 МАХСУС СОН

ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ
СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫЙ НОМЕР 1

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL
SPECIAL ISSUE 1

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Тадқиқот город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000